

BUILDING A UNIDIRECTIONAL SHAKE TABLE FROM SCRATCH

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Abstract

Nepal, which lies under the Indian and Tibetan tectonic plates, is a seismically active region continuously facing a high risk of life and structural damage. In this context, the development of low-cost unidirectional shake tables is very important for research on the improvement of seismic resilience structure and promoting earthquake engineering. The shake table simulates the one-directional (horizontal) motion of the ground during a seismic activity. Using cost-effective procedures and locally available material, the fabrication of a unidirectional shake table will play a vital role in research on the improvement of seismic-resistant structures. The designed shake table is driven by a mechanical actuator and is operated under variable speed showcasing different frequencies of ground motion. The simple crank-slider mechanism is used to convert the circular motion of the actuator into the linear motion of the platform of the unidirectional shake table. This article covers design consideration, material selection, mechanical design and construction, assembly instructions, and future upgrade potential, of a unidirectional shake table showcasing the shake table's contribution to earthquake precautions.

Keywords – *Unidirectional Shake Table, Seismic Resilience, Low-cost Design, Crank-Slider Mechanism*

1. Introduction

The Shake Table is a simple mechanism that simulates the motion of the ground surface during an earthquake.

A blog "*What is a shake table and why did we test our systems on one?*, 2024" noted that:

The shake table is a tried and trusted piece of equipment that simulates the forces experienced during an earthquake. The earliest shake table was invented at the University of Tokyo in 1893 and ran on a simple wheel mechanism. Modern tables are much more sophisticated and consist of a large platform that can move horizontally and vertically in different directions to replicate the ground motion caused during a seismic event. (p. 4)

After each strong seismic event, the knowledge on the earthquake response of structures is greatly increased by the observation and analysis of behavior of the different types of constructions (*Danish et al.*, 2019). Shake table subjects' structures to controlled earthquake

conditions, thereby facilitating in-depth analysis of their performance during seismic events (Candeias *et al.*, 2023). This includes determining of point of failure, the nature of failure, the seismic capacity of the structure, and how and when any structural component fails under seismic loading. These applications provide certain ideas, designs, or concepts for developing better, stable, and safe structural components.

2. Design Considerations

Although multi-directional shake table is far better than unidirectional shake table, the importance of unidirectional shake table is as equal as of multi directional shake table. A unidirectional shake table is easier to fabricate as compared to multi directional one.

Parameter	Description	Why It Matters
Max Displacement	140 mm	Determines how much a platform can move
Frequency Range	0.5 Hz – 5 Hz	Simulates various earthquake wave frequency
Payload Capacity	Up to 40 kg	How much weight it can safely shake
Motion Type	Single axis (Y direction)	Showcases the direction of motion
Actuation type	DC geared motor with crank-slider	Controls precision and motion range
Source Converter	Switch Mode Power Supply (SMPS)	Converts 220V AC supply to 24V DC supply for DC motor
Control Interface	PWM control	Easy control system
Motion of Platform	Unidirectional Caster wheel	For deviation-less & vibration free motion. Used at top, bottom & outside of frame.

3. Materials and Components Required

The following is a categorized list of the essential materials and components needed to construct a unidirectional shake table.

3.1 Structural and Mechanical Components

The structural and mechanical components used in building a unidirectional shake table is showcased in the table below:

Item	Specification	Purpose
Base Frame Material	Mild Steel Square Pipe, MSSP (3.5cm × 3.5cm)	Provides rigid foundation for the system
Moving Platform	Plywood (16mm thick)	Serves as the platform for mounting test models
Linear Guide Rails	MSSP as a rail. Caster wheels are mounted at top, bottom and outside of MSSP.	Enables smooth, constrained unidirectional motion
Crank-Slider	Disc/MS Flat	Converts rotary motion to linear displacement
Fasteners and Mounts	Screws, bolts, nuts	Required for assembly and secure mounting

3.2 Actuation System

The actuation system of a shake table varies based on its load capacity and performance requirements. For reduced-scale structures, simple motor-driven mechanisms may be sufficient, while larger or high-performance tables may require more powerful systems. The choice depends on factors such as structures' weight, desired displacement, frequency range, and budget.

Component	Specification	Purpose
Electric Motor	24 Volts, 250 Watt DC Geared E-bike motor with rated speed of 300 rpm (weight 3.2 kg)	Drives the shaking motion
Power Supply unit	Switch Mode Power Supply (220V AC to 24V DC)	Supplies power to the motor and control system

3.3 Control and Electronics

Component	Specification	Purpose
PWM control	24V capacity PWM controller	Allows frequency/amplitude adjustment

3.4 Miscellaneous

- 16 AWG Silicon Wire
- Switch for on/off
- Paints, brushes for aesthetics
- 2 pin plug

4. Tools Required

4.1 Basic Hand tools

- Screwdrivers
- Pliers
- Files
- Hammer
- Punch
- Adjustable Wrench

4.2 Power Tools

- Electric Drill
- Welding Machine
- Metal Cut-off saw
- Grinder
- Soldering Iron Kit

4.3 Measuring and Marking Tools

- Metallic Tape/Ruler
- Marker

5. Mechanical Design and Construction

5.1 Design of Linear motion mechanisms

Mild Steel flats of 3mm thickness are used for clamping unidirectional caster wheel. Holes in MS Flats are made using electric drill and caster wheels are assembled using nuts and bolts. For smooth, deviation-less and vibration-free motion, these assembled

members are also placed outside and bottom of the guide rail (MSSP). Then these members are welded with MS flats for rigidity. Mild Steel metallic disc is connected in the axle of motor and the lever/crank is connected at a distance of 10cm from the center of the disc. This particular arrangement converts circular motion into linear motion displacing platform $\pm 10\text{cm}$ from the center.

pic: 3D design and construction of linear motion arrangement of Unidirectional Shake Table

5.2 Design of Guide Rails and Frame

Mild Steel Square Pipes (MSSP) of $3.5\text{cm} \times 3.5\text{cm}$ cross section are used for the frame. The out to out dimension of frame is $90\text{cm} \times 70\text{cm} \times 30\text{cm}$. The top most MSSP of frame is used as guide rail over which platform of shake table displaces. The type of connection used for frame is weld.

pic: 3D design and construction of base frame with linear motion arrangement

5.3 Design of Platform

Plywood of dimension $100\text{cm} \times 100\text{cm} \times 1.6\text{cm}$ is used as a platform for unidirectional shake table. Platform and the MS flats for linear motion are connected using nuts and bolts.

pic: 3D design and construction of Unidirectional Shake Table

6. Assembly Instructions

Brief instructions for the assembly of different components of the unidirectional shake table are listed below:

6.1 Mechanical Assembly

- At first, Mild Steel Square Pipes are taken and welded to make a frame of the specified dimension.
- Then 6 pieces of Mild Steel Flats of specified dimensions are taken and drilled using an electric drill in order to clamp the caster wheel.
- A total of 12 caster wheels are then bolted with MS flats. Each 3 sets of these bolted caster wheels and flats are then welded for each guide rail.
- Then, each of the linear motion arrangements for each guide rail is connected with the help of MS flats.
- Holes on the connecting MS Flats are made to connect the platform of the shake table for displacement.
- The axle of the DC motor is connected to a disc/crank in which a lever/connecting rod of a specified dimension is mounted.
- Another end of the lever/connecting rod is connected to the projection of the MS flat at the center with nut and bolt.

6.2 Electrical Assembly

- Wires from the AC source are connected to the Live (L) and Neutral (N) port of Switch Mode Power Supply of 24V DC.
- Similarly, +V and -V ports are connected with silicon wire for DC load (motor).
- In between the motor and Switch Mode Power Supply, a switch for the on/off mechanism is connected.
- In between the motor and switch, a PWM speed controller is connected.

fig: Wiring diagram for Unidirectional Shake Table

7. Budget

S.N.	Description	Unit	Quantity	Rate (NRs.)	Amount (NRs.)
1.	24V, 250W DC Geared E bike Motor	pcs	1	6,000	6,000
2.	Switch Mode Power Supply (220V AC to 24V DC Converter)	pcs	1	6,500	6,500
3.	Unidirectional caster wheel	pcs	14	70	980
4.	PWM speed controller	pcs	1	240	240
5.	Small switch	pcs	1	20	20
6.	16 AWG Silicone wire	m	3	370	1,110
7.	MS Square Pipe (4cm × 4cm)	kg	17	125	2,125
8.	MS Flat Bars (2.5cm × 2mm)	kg	5	100	500
9.	Plywood (12mm thick)	sq.m	1	1,000	1,000
10.	Miscellaneous				2,000
Total					20,475

In words: Twenty thousand four hundred and seventy five rupees only

8. Future Improvements and Upgrades

- Conversion from unidirectional motion to multi-directional motion.
- Application of sensors.
- App integration for seismic wave input and output.
- Data logging and visualization.

9. Conclusion

"Building a unidirectional shake table from scratch" is a valuable attempt that integrates mechanical design, electrical control, and structural engineering principles. During this process, one gains practical knowledge and experience regarding machine handling, and seismicity and understands how the structure behaves under seismic activity when subjected to seismic waves. This project not only opens a platform for research and testing of the reduced-scaled structure but also promotes earthquake engineering in the context of Nepal. Despite multiple limitations, this successful design and construction of a unidirectional shake table opens a portal advancing earthquake-resistant design and improving the safety of the structure.

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